

HIGH PRECISION GNSS-INCLINABLE SURVEYING POLE WITH LOW-COST IMUS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the iPOLE patented invention. iPOLE is designed to be used as a new tool, a sustained invention in topographic surveying. Nowadays topographic surveying works in outdoor environments rely mainly on Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) based poles. They provide with a faster position computation and, thus a faster topographic survey. The theoretical basis behind the surveying pole is to compute the GNSS antenna position through a geodetic GNSS receiver and later on to project the point to the ground. In order to properly perform this projection, the pole needs to be completely vertical. Unfortunately, there are situations where the environment thus not allow to place the pole in the required vertical position so the use of the tool is not possible. A solution relying on fusion of inertial sensors and magnetometers to overcome this problem has become quite extended in the last years. The solution allows to work in tilted mode but still suffer from critical restrictions, mainly when the works need to be done near strong magnetic fields (like railways or electric power stations). With iPOLE we want to go a step beyond those solutions by applying the fundamentals of aircrafts positioning technology to surveying. The idea behind iPOLE relies on actual rise on the market of low-cost medium performance inertial sensors. iPOLE overcomes the magnetic field limitations and allows using the GNSS-based pole in any position, not just in a vertical one, and independently of the presence of magnetic fields. Analogously to aircraft positioning systems, iPOLE integrates inertial sensors and GNSS. Moreover, iPOLE takes also advantage of the topographic pole and deals with all those information in a novel way such that, in open space and not strongly magnetized scenarios, it is able to locate ground points with the same accuracy as current topographic systems. Furthermore, in half-occluded spaces or spaces with strong magnetic fields, where classical solution is not able to provide solution, iPOLE provides solution with topographic acceptable performance thus extending the operability of this tool.

Key words: GNSS, inclinable surveying pole, low-cost IMUs.

INTRODUCTION

Surveying poles are topographic instruments used to measure with high precision and accuracy a ground point coordinates [1] [2]. Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) surveying poles obtain the GNSS antenna phase-centre coordinates (top of the pole) through a geodetic GNSS receiver and later on project these coordinates to the ground point (bottom of the pole or tip). Classical surveying poles operate in a vertical mode and the projection is obtained by subtracting the pole length into the height component of the measured GNSS point. This operation requires the user to level the pole perpendicular to ground plane, usually aid by some kind of analogue or digital bubbles or similar devices.

Nowadays some surveying poles can operate in a tilt mode by adding sensing elements and measuring the inclination or three-dimensional orientation (also now as attitude). The orientation of a pole is defined by three rotation angles named heading, pitch and roll, shown below in Fig. 1. Heading (or yaw) is the angle which defines a rotation around the vertical axis (z-axis); Pitch is the angle which defines a rotation around the horizontal axis (y-axis), moving the pole forward or backward; and Roll is the angle which defines a rotation around the horizontal axis (x-axis), moving the pole right or left. Most of these new devices rely at least on a set of inertial sensors or similar (i.e. orthogonal triad) and may include a magnetic sensor for global heading orientation.

Fig. 1. Rotation angles definition (left) and oblique orientation and its main benefit on satellite view (centre and right).

The main objective of the research presented on this paper is to propose an alternative and patented approach to tilting pole systems, able to provide requested performance even when working near magnetic fields with a simple operation procedure. The proposed solution relies on a GNSS receiver with Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) capability and a low-cost inertial navigation system (INS). This INS system uses MicroElectroMechanical Systems (MEMS) technology and comprises an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU). The advantages of using inclinable poles systems include measuring coordinates in harsh environments, considered inaccessible until now such as corners of buildings, walls, areas that are steep, dangerous, hidden or difficult to access, to mention a few. In addition, this procedure achieves better accurate results subtracting the human component error on the measurements due to a non-perfect pole level (verticality). Furthermore, the fact that users do not need to level the pole for measuring GNSS coordinates leads into a faster acquisition procedure, increasing the campaign productivity.

Most of the current GNSS-inclinable surveying pole systems rely on magnetometer sensors such as the Trimble R10. It can stand up to 15 degrees of tilting [3]. The use of a magnetic sensor will degrade the pole performance when operating near magnetic fields making the results unreliable, but it provides an easy and fast global orientation. In addition, magnetometer based tilted poles require a calibration methodology, i.e. rotating the system over the three different axis (12 different orientations) [4]. Many more poles based on magnetic sensors are offered by other companies such as Topcon (Hiper HR) [5], Stonex (S10A) [6] and South (Galaxy G6) [7]. All these poles and their positioning specifications offered by each manufacturer itself are shown in Table 1. Other GNSS-inclinable surveying pole systems may use an expensive high-grade IMU.

Table 1. Some of the most popular surveying poles and their positioning specifications.

Trimble R10		
Parameter	Value (typ.)	Units
Code differential positioning	0.25 (H) ; 0.5 (V)	[m]
Precision static GNSS surveying	3 (H) ; 3.5 (V)	[mm]
Static and fast static GNSS surveying	3 (H) ; 5 (V)	[mm]
RTK baseline < 30 km	8 (H) ; 15 (V)	[mm]
Network RTK (2-8 seconds start-up time)	8 (H) ; 15 (V)	[mm]
Maximum tilt	15	degrees
Topcon Hiper HR		
Parameter	Value (typ.)	Units
Precision static GNSS surveying	3 (H) ; 3.5 (V)	[mm]
Static and fast static GNSS surveying	3 (H) ; 5 (V)	[mm]
RTK baseline < 30 km	5 (H) ; 10 (V)	[mm]
Maximum tilt	15	degrees
Stonex S10A		
Parameter	Value (typ.)	Units
Code differential positioning	0.25 (H) ; 0.45 (V)	[m]
Precision static GNSS surveying	2.5 (H) ; 3.5 (V)	[mm]
Static and fast static GNSS surveying	3 (H) ; 5 (V)	[mm]
RTK baseline < 10 km (< 10 seconds start-up time)	8 (H) ; 15 (V)	[mm]
Maximum tilt	35	degrees
Initialisation	< 15	[s]

South Galaxy G6		
Parameter	Value (typ.)	Units
Code differential positioning	0.25 (H) ; 0.5 (V)	[m]
Precision static GNSS surveying	2.5 + 1*km (between meas.)	[mm]
RTK baseline < 30 km	8	[mm]
Maximum tilt	30	degrees
Initialisation	< 10	[s]
Leica GS18 R10 (it does not include a magnetometer)		
Parameter	Value (typ.)	Units
Code differential positioning	0.25 (H) ; 0.25 (V)	[m]
RTK baseline < 30 km	8 (H) ; 15 (V)	[mm]
Network RTK (2-8 seconds start-up time)	8 (H) ; 15 (V)	[mm]
RTK Tilt compensated	10 + 0.7/tilt(°)	[mm]
Static with long observations	3 (H) ; 3.5 (V)	[mm]
Static and rapid static	3 (H) ; 5 (V)	[mm]
RTK Initial Convergence time	20 – 40 (< 1 recovery)	[min]
Initialisation	4	[s]

Hence, most of the top surveying companies already commercialize their own GNSS-inclinable surveying poles based mainly on low-cost IMU sensors, such as Leica GS18 T [8]. It do not uses magnetic sensors and the IMU is initialized (*aka* calibrated) [9]. The product present here is an alternative approach. At least, both Leica and Trimble products take advantage of satellite RTK corrections to provide global RTK coverage. Satellite RTK corrections and other extra functionalities are out of the scope of this research and invention.

The key point of the proposed research is based on the IMU initialization procedure, patented on 2015 with the international application number PCT/EP2015/081433 (WO2017114577A1). The main objective is to estimate the bias of the accelerometers and gyroscopes each time the surveying pole is turned on. Pitch and roll angles can be easily estimated with a static acquisition by relating the accelerometer values to the Earth's gravitational force. The challenging orientation parameter to estimate is the heading angle. The initialization procedure consists on maintaining the tip of the pole on a single point in the ground while inclining the pole into different angles, at least in three different orientations, in example, tilting the pole in pitch twice and once in roll. Considering that the ground coordinate is the same at the different pole inclinations, the heading, pitch and roll orientation angles of the pole are estimated using least squares method. The set of equations relate the RTK GNSS receiver coordinates to the ground coordinate with the pole length and orientation. By determining the pole orientation angles, the accelerometer and gyroscope biases can be obtained. In comparison with the existent solutions, the proposed initialization procedure is simple, fast and effective and it does not require the user to move to another ground point.

Once the system is initialized the user can perform point projection as a normal GNSS-inclinable surveying pole by using the loosely coupling mechanization equations. The IMU initialization procedure needs to be performed every time the system is powered on due to the bias instability. Furthermore, the bias instability changes the initial estimated biases along time operation, i.e. due to time drifts and other source of errors, so the system needs to be periodically recalibrated to ensure the accuracy of the system.

The projection error that is added by tilting the pole depends mainly on the pole length, on the tilt angle and on the IMU performance. For example, by using a 2 meters pole, a maximum tilt angle of 20 degrees and a low-cost IMU (Invensense MPU9250) the projection error is about 2 cm (obtained from simulations, see chapter with the simulations results).

The main conclusion reached is that using this methodology it is possible to use a GNSS-inclinable surveying pole with a low-cost inertial sensor within the GNSS RTK accuracy specifications. It is possible to estimate the IMU biases and the pole absolute orientation, to guarantee the surveying pole performance, using a fast and simple initialization procedure. This new technology and methodology adds the tilt capabilities to the current surveying poles at a low price by implementing a consumer grade IMU and taking profit of the GNSS RTK position. In addition, this method is robust in any outdoor environment even with magnetic fields disturbances. This new challenging surveying system is capable to measure GNSS coordinates in places that previously was inaccessible.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The pole comprises hardware components which operate according to an algorithm, or software, for performing improved position determination. The process is performed iteratively by a Kalman filter, which is initialized by a first information set which is then continually updated periodically sequentially in time. At periodic time intervals, or every time new inertial data or satellite positioning GNSS data is available, the Kalman filter of the positioning device recalculates the orientation angles and positions.

The acquisition comprises an initialization step for initial ground point position and orientation estimation. The processing further comprises timing for time-tagging the position data as well as the navigation and inertial data. The initial ground point estimation is determined by solving the following least squares problem wherein the antenna point coordinates and the ground point coordinates are related through the pole length. The distance difference between the two points is always the pole length:

$$L = | X_i - X_g | \quad (1)$$

where L is the known pole length, X_i are the GNSS antenna geodetic coordinates of i th-step and X_g is the geodetic coordinates of the ground point which has to be determined. Next, the ground point is more accurately determined by obtaining at least two other ground point estimations at two different pole orientations, or attitudes. This is done by tilting the pole in different directions and estimating the ground point. The final ground point is based on the result of at least three data sets. The at least three data sets provide position and orientation angle related information to determine with certainty the position of the ground point.

A GNSS antenna connected to a GNSS receiver and an IMU are the core data providers of the system. The raw satellite data is used to determine the GNSS coordinates of the top end by using differential processing. This can be achieved by either using a GNSS receiver including differential processing capabilities; applying real time kinetic corrections in real-time from an RTK processor; or apply such differential processing off-line, in a post-processing stage.

An inertial sensor, or inertial measurement unit IMU, is an electronic device that measures and reports specific forces and angular rates exerted on a body, using a combination of three accelerometers and three gyroscopes. It is connected to the processing by a digital communication interface. An accelerometer measures acceleration forces based on Newton's second law "The acceleration of a body is parallel and directly proportional to the net applied force F and inversely proportional to its mass m ". Typically, acceleration units are expressed in meters per second per second (m/s^2). A gyroscope measures angular rotation increments from a reference orientation. Gyroscopes are based on the Coriolis effect, measuring the deflection force (F_c) of moving objects when they are rotating through a reference frame. Typically, gyroscope units are expressed in degrees per second (deg/s) thus expressing angular velocities. The accelerometers and gyroscopes are oriented orthogonally to each other, being measured three different axis (x , y and z). The inertial sensor generates inertial data comprising three lineal accelerations and three angular velocities (one for each axis). The inertial data necessary for subsequently determining the orientation of the positioning pole.

The accelerometer sensor biases are determined by defining a vector of accelerometer biases based on the following formula:

$$B_{acc} = a^b - RM(\Theta, \alpha, \beta) \cdot (0,0,g)^T \quad (2)$$

Where B_{acc} is the (unknown) vector representing the bias of the accelerometer in the body frame. The vector a^b is the (known) mean values of sensed accelerations from the inertial sensor (in a body forward-right-down, or bfrd, configuration) in the first calibration step, RM is the (known) rotation matrix between the local reference frame and the body reference frame and g is the Earth's gravitational force ($\sim 9.81 m/s^2$). In this expression, the accelerometer sensor bias values are determined, in a static position, based on the unique force measured being the gravity force. The force can be distributed in the three axes so a rotation matrix is needed to transform the local reference frame to the body reference frame.

Next, the vector of gyroscope bias values are determined based on the following formula:

$$B_{gyro} = \omega^b - R_E^B \cdot (0,0,w)^T \quad (3)$$

Where B_{gyro} is the (unknown) vector representing the bias of the gyroscopes in the body frame. The vector w^b is the (known) mean values of sensed angular velocities from the inertial sensor (also in a bfrd configuration) in the first calibration step, R^B_E is the (known) rotation matrix between the Earth-Centred Earth-Fixed (ECEF) reference frame and the body reference frame and ω is the velocity rotation of the earth equal to 15 degrees by hour. The gyroscope sensor biases are determined, in a static position, by knowing that the unique angular rotation measured is the rotation of the earth. The angular velocity can be distributed in the three axes so a rotation matrix is needed to transform the ECEF reference frame to the body reference frame.

Once these bias values are computed, they are subtracted from the inertial data readings in order to compensate for this sensor systematic error. First, inertial data samples are obtained for at least three pole inclinations. From the inertial data at any one inclination, the pitch and roll of the surveying pole may be determined. The pitch angle is determined as the arc sinus of the measured acceleration in the x-axis of the body-frame divided by the constant Earth's gravitational force. The roll angle is determined as the arc sinus of the measured acceleration in the y-axis of the body-frame divided by the constant Earth's gravitational. The following equations show these calculations:

$$\alpha = -\text{asin}(a_x/g) \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \text{asin}(a_y/g) \quad (5)$$

Where α is the pitch angle, β is the roll angle, a_x is the mean acceleration measured in the x-axis, a_y is the mean acceleration measured in the y-axis and g is the Earth's gravitational force. Hence, the pitch and the roll orientation angles are determined based on mean acceleration data of the x-axis and the y-axis, respectively.

For every inclination of the pole, a plurality of ground point candidates emerge as the plurality of possible intersections of the vertical projection with the horizontal projection of the pole's top end:

$$\text{Vertical projection} = \iota \cdot \cos(\beta) \cdot \cos(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Horizontal projection} = \iota \cdot \sin(\beta) \cdot \sin(\alpha) \quad (7)$$

Where ι is the pole length, α is the pitch angle and β is the roll angle.

The vertical projection is the result of multiplying the pole length with the cosine of the roll and the cosine of the pitch. The horizontal projection is the result of multiplying the pole length with the sine of the roll and the sine of the pitch. From this plurality of ground point candidates corresponding to each pole inclination, the final ground point position corresponds to the candidate which is common to, at least three, different pole inclinations, or attitudes. In other words, it is the candidate which coincides with all pole inclinations. Fig. 2 depicts the pole at three different inclinations, or attitudes (GNSS points 1 to 3, right side). The point at which the candidate ground point is the same for all three inclinations is the final ground point. In the depiction of Fig. 2, this corresponds with the point of intersection of the three circles, each circle corresponding to the plurality of candidates possible at each pole attitude. Hence, a minimum of three ground point candidates are necessary in order to determine the final ground point value with certainty.

Fig. 2. Pole ground point determination.

A position-determining device is provided on a surveying pole, which works accurately even in magnetized environments as it does not make use of magnetometers. Moreover, due to its simple design, it is economic and requires minimal processing resources. This determination using the minimum of three sampling points is accurate and also simple and fast.

The reference timing for time tagging the raw data acquired is processor core own clock. However, this reference clock is quite unstable and therefore needs to be stabilized. This stabilization is achieved by using the pulse-per-second (PPS) timing signal provided by the GNSS receiver and is implemented by a simple correction algorithm always running. The processor clock drift is compensated by this PPS signal, at one-second intervals, in order to maintain a good reference time-stamp, resulting in an accurate time tagging. The data processing is responsible for determining the ground point position using the data determined from the acquisition means as input to the Kalman filter.

In case it is desired to determine the position of a second, or further, ground point, it would normally be necessary to repeat the initialization for the new ground points, once for every new ground point. However, in another aspect of the invention, once a first ground point is measured, it is possible to internally track the difference till a new ground point and hence determine the geographic coordinates of new ground points without performing another initialization phase. This is achieved by determining, in the initialization stage, also the absolute heading of the pole with respect to the geographic North.

Hence, when in a new position, the new ground point position can be derived based on the previous and the new heading information. Although the pitch and roll may be determined directly from the inertial data, the absolute heading cannot be determined directly, as only relative information is available. In a next step, the heading, or absolute North, is determined, using the data from the at least three samples as well as the determined ground point.

Therefore, a simple user-friendly algorithm permits, in a first initialization phase, any specialized or non-specialized user to initialize the device when in line-of-sight contact with GNSS satellites. In a subsequent operational phase, the user may continue using the surveying pole in environments without line-of-sight contact with satellites, as the internal tracking mechanism permits computing the pitch, roll and heading as well as the geodesic coordinates of the pole at all times.

Fig. 2 depicts the process of determining the absolute heading using the data sets of three sampling points, or attitudes. In this aspect, the absolute heading angle (Θ), or the angle with respect to the geographic north, is determined based on pitch, roll, vertical projection, and horizontal projection determined from the at least three initial data samples. The heading (Θ) is determined by projecting each GNSS point to the known ground point at each of at least three attitude angles by using a rotation matrix (containing the heading, pitch and roll angles) and using a translation vector (the pole distance):

$$\mathbf{X}_g = \mathbf{X}_i + \mathbf{RM}(\Theta, \alpha, \beta) \cdot \mathbf{Tv}(0,0,L) \quad (8)$$

where L is the pole length, α is the pitch angle, β is the roll angle, Θ is the (unknown) heading angle, \mathbf{X}_i is the GNSS antenna geodetic coordinates of i th-step, \mathbf{X}_g is the geodetic coordinates of the ground point which has to be determined, \mathbf{RM} is the rotation matrix and \mathbf{Tv} is the translation vector. Once the heading is determined, subsequent position determinations do not need initialization steps and can be performed very fast.

At this point, the process of determining the position and orientation by the surveying pole is completed as it saves the coordinates of the ground point, as well as the orientation of the pole, comprising the heading, pitch, and roll angles and all the data obtained.

First, a simulation process started to face an initial validation of the invention. Both inertial and GNSS data was simulated using own CTTC's GEMMA system [10]. In order to see the performance of the envisaged system, the inertial data was modelled according to the specifications of an RTK GNSS receiver and two different IMUs: an EPSON M-G352PDE1 [11], from now on referred simply as Epson, and an Invensense MPU9250A [12], from now on referred as MPU9250. The first one is in the unitary price range of few thousand euros at the moment of this writing. The second one is one thousand time cheaper, easily found by only few euros and very popular on low cost inertial-based products and prototypes. In those simulations, the calibration and acquisition procedures were emulated for two different environments: open sky and urban environment.

Second, an early-prototype was built to capture some real data and validate some basic experiments. The system core modules and its main architecture are shown in Fig. 3 (top and bottom, respectively).

Fig. 3. Block diagram (top) and architecture (bottom) of iPOLE.

Current microprocessor passes by far the hardware requirements to execute this particular task but keeping the sensors in the expected range or category (MEMS IMU and Geodetic grade GNSS receiver and antenna). An A53 64 bits ARMv8 processor with wireless connectivity (for RTK corrections) is placed on the top of the pole just below the GNSS antenna. It implements a socket communication between the two main microprocessor threads, one for the acquisition and time tag of the raw data and another for the data processing. The user has a single button to start the surveying campaign and to control the system initialization steps.

RESULTS

As mentioned before, results are divided between simulations and real (outdoor) tests.

Simulations

In the next table a summary of the errors obtained when using the algorithm with simulated data are presented. When working in open space with good GNSS visibility, this is, more than six satellites and with no multipath, the error on the computed ground point is below two centimetres whatever IMU are we using. In the case of more complex environments, when only 5 satellites are available and some multipath effects arise, both solutions are acceptable, although the one with the MPU unit is slightly below the desired performance.

Table 2. iPOLE performance with simulated data.

Environment	Open Sky		Urban	
	Epson	MPU	Epson	MPU
Inertial unit				
Error Lon (σ) - cm	1.4	1.2	1.5	2.9
Error Lat (σ) - cm	1.0	1.2	2.2	4.8
Error Height (σ) - cm	0.7	1.2	1.8	1.8

Outdoor Tests

In this section the main results obtained with iPOLE prototype where presented. Please, note that the tests where only carried out with the IMU of higher grade, this is the Epson IMU. When working in friendly environment, the iPOLE system works properly and provide errors below three centimetres. When working in hard environments, in this case, the measurements where collected besides a wall, the system performance decrease, but is still acceptable for topographic works.

Table 3. iPOLE (Epson) performance with real data.

Environment	Open Sky	Urban
Inertial unit	Epson	Epson
Error Lon (σ) – cm	2.4	5.5
Error Lat (σ) – cm	2.8	4.2
Error Height (σ) - cm	2.7	5.8

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented the idea behind the iPOLE system, a patented invention. Based on the current state-of-the-art and the available technologies, we have designed a system that combines inertial data and RTK data to achieve good enough results to be used for static surveying. The first simulations and data acquisitions allow us to be optimistic on the suitability of the system. The short-term stability of the sensors and the proper performance of RTK solution is good enough to be used in a system that can be recalibrated once or twice per hour. Despite of the promising preliminary results, the project still needs more tests on difficult environments.

Although the performance provided by competitors (main tilting pole manufacturers, see) specify sub-centimetric errors in differential RTK mode, both our simulated and field results show that the iPOLE product may fit better in the range of a centimetre (or few) error range. This is considered enough as the invention clearly focuses on the use of low cost inertial sensors. Furthermore, best performance when operating surveying systems is obtained more likely with a tripod instead of a pole, thus reducing mechanical instabilities and improving the overall performance but difficulting its operation.

Moreover, has been noticed from the many validation field tests, that the early-prototype unit will require of a better and a more accurate design to minimize errors due to mechanical constraints and minor lever-arm miscalculations.

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